

Demographic Statistics for the Datasets in “Outlier detection for foot complaint diagnosis: modeling confounding factors using metric learning”

Demographic	Statistic	Dataset		
		Training Data	Healthy Subjects	Hallux Valgus Patients
Age (years)	mean	36.8	42.3	54.5
	std. dev.	12.9	16.8	16.1
	max	68	70	74
	min	18	18	18
Weight (kg)	mean	74.8	74.8	69.9
	std. dev.	14.0	12.2	12.4
	max	144.0	103.2	96.9
	min	47.0	50.6	42.4
Height (cm)	mean	175.6	175.0	170.3
	std. dev.	9.2	9.8	7.8
	max	202	195	189
	min	150	159	149
Shoe Size (UK)	mean	8.2	8.0	7.4
	std. dev.	2.2	2.6	2.3
	max	13.0	14.5	15.5
	min	2.0	4.5	2.5
Sex	no. male	275	21	6
	no. female	155	34	44

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 2 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 2 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 2 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 19 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 19 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 19 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 19 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 19 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 19 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 39 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 39 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 39 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 39 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 39 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 39 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 41 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 41 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 41 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 41 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 41 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 51 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 51 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 51 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 51 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 51 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 51 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 52 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 52 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 52 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 52 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 52 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 52 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 53 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 53 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 53 (left foot)

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Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 53 (right foot)

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Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 53 (right foot)

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Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 53 (right foot)

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Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 54 (left foot)

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Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

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Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 54 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

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Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 54 (left foot)

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Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 54 (right foot)

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Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 54 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 54 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 55 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 55 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 55 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 55 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 55 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

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Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 1 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 3 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 4 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 5 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 6 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 7 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 8 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 9 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 10 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 11 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 12 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 13 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 14 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 15 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 16 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 17 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 18 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 20 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 21 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 22 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 23 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 24 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 25 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 26 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 27 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 28 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 29 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 30 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 31 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 32 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 33 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 34 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 35 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 36 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 37 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 38 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 40 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 42 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 43 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 44 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 45 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 46 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 47 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 48 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 49 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (left foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (ML)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (ML)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (ML)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (IID)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (IID)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (IID)

Measured Plantar Pressures, Patient 50 (right foot)

Predicted Baseline Mean Image (1D)

Predicted Baseline Standard Deviation (1D)

Z-Scores of Detected Outliers (1D)

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